

Measuring Irregular Migration

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Visualising the Irregular Migrant Population of Europe and North America

MIRreM Technical Note

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1	22/07/2025	Denis Kierans	UOXF	Submitted Version 1

Summary

This document sets out the background, online location and description of a series of interactive visualisations and webpages, which present data, analysis and other information about irregular migration.

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THE MIRREM PROJECT

MIRreM examines estimates and statistical indicators on the irregular migrant population in Europe as well as related policies, including the regularisation of migrants in irregular situations.

MIRreM analyses policies defining migrant irregularity, stakeholders' data needs and usage, and assesses existing estimates and statistical indicators on irregular migration in the countries under study and at the EU level. Using several coordinated pilots, the project develops new and innovative methods for measuring irregular migration and explores if and how these instruments can be applied in other socio-economic or institutional contexts. Based on a broad mapping of regularisation practices in the EU as well as detailed case studies, MIRreM will develop 'regularisation scenarios' to better understand conditions under which regularisation should be considered as a policy option. Together with expert groups that will be set up on irregular migration data and regularisation, respectively, the project will synthesise findings into a Handbook on data on irregular migration and a Handbook on pathways out of irregularity. The project's research covers 20 countries, including 12 EU countries, Canada, the United Kingdom and the United States.

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KEYWORDS

Irregular Migration; Statistics; Data Visualisation

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 RATIONALE

One of the primary aims of the MIRreM project is to contribute to better data on irregular migration. With this in mind, WP4 brought together teams from across the MIRreM project, as well as partners from academia, policy and practice, to develop an online database which contains and assesses the quality of estimates of irregular migrants living in European and North American countries between 2008 and 2023 (Kierans et al, 2025). Researchers from WP4 then analysed these data and presented their findings in a working paper, *The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe* (Kierans and Vargas-Silva, 2024).

We recognize that our mission to foster ‘better data’ on irregular migration speaks not only the fidelity of the data, among other important aspects, but also to communicating and using them fairly and responsibly. As such, we developed a series of infographics and webpages featuring the data collected and assessed under WP4 of the project, the findings of the related working paper, and relevant publications from across the project more broadly. In doing so, we hope to present this information in a nuanced and accessible format, making it easier for a wider audience to access, understand and ultimately engage with the data and findings more easily than they might with more traditional dissemination formats, such as reports and databases.

1.2 DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

With this aim of engaging data users, and recognising that the MIRreM project was continuing to produce and refine outputs, we revisited our original plan to produce a static infographic presenting the findings of WP4. Instead, we opted to create an updateable, interactive online dashboard that would:

1. Display key estimates on irregular migrant stocks in a user-friendly map format, likely using Tableau;
2. Link these estimates to selected metadata, such as year, source and quality;
3. Provide context for these data through brief methodological explanations and related publications from across the project;
4. Allow users to ‘dive deeper’ by viewing the data in table format, downloading the data in a commonly used format, and click through to the full underlying dataset on Zenodo;

5. Create individual country pages presenting all available national estimates alongside relevant publications from across the project;
6. Enable access for visually impaired users and on a variety of devices.

Throughout 2024, the evolving design and approach were presented and discussed in several MIrreM Steering Group and Consortium meetings, including an in-person full-project meeting in Potsdam and subsequent online exchanges. The author worked closely with a developer at youngminds to incorporate feedback from these meetings, adapting the structure and content.

Tableau was used to display the top line findings from WP4 on the Data Portal due to its capacity to handle multi-dimensional data and to support multi-faceted, interactive dashboards. Unlike simpler visualisation tools, Tableau allows for flexible filtering, dynamic highlighting, and the integration of multiple chart types within a single view. It has the capacity to visualise irregular migration estimates by country, year, estimation method, and confidence range, all within an intuitive and responsive interface. Tableau is compatible with the content management system (CMS) of the MIrreM website and supports accessible design features, such as colour palettes suitable for colour-blind users. It is updated centrally, via Tableau Public, allowing the project team to maintain and expand the portal efficiently over time without having to make changes to the webpage itself, and additional dashboards can be created – all of which may prove useful as the project continues to generate and refine data and outputs. The author's familiarity with Tableau and Tableau Public was yet another advantage.

In parallel with the Data Portal, a set of 20 country pages was developed to present the fully array of national-level stock estimates compiled and assessed under the MIrreM project and related information in a user-friendly format.

The interactive charts embedded on each country page were developed using Flourish, a web-based data visualisation tool suitable for creating simple, responsive graphics. Flourish was selected for its ease of use, compatibility with the website's CMS, good adaptivity across devices, and ability to be updated without having to make changes to the webpage itself. We chose the faster-loading Flourish over Tableau because a complex dashboard was not required for the country pages, and Flourish still supports many of the features we prioritised, such as linking back to the original data source and interactive tooltips.

1.3 ACCESS

The Data Portal is located at <https://irregularmigration.eu/data-portal/>. It visualises the irregular migration stock estimates and analysis on a dashboard that features a clickable map and bar charts, as well as in table format. Furthermore, it acts as a central hub, showcasing other content and linking to the country pages.

The country pages, which picture the full array of estimates and related publications on a country-by-country basis, can be accessed here:

- Austria: <https://irregularmigration.eu/austria/>
- Belgium: <https://irregularmigration.eu/belgium/>
- Bosnia and Herzegovina: <https://irregularmigration.eu/bosnia-and-herzegovina/>
- Canada: <https://irregularmigration.eu/canada/>
- Finland: <https://irregularmigration.eu/finland/>
- France: <https://irregularmigration.eu/france/>
- Germany: <https://irregularmigration.eu/germany/>
- Greece: <https://irregularmigration.eu/greece/>
- Ireland: <https://irregularmigration.eu/ireland/>
- Italy: <https://irregularmigration.eu/italy/>
- Morocco: <https://irregularmigration.eu/morocco/>
- The Netherlands: <https://irregularmigration.eu/netherlands/>
- Poland: <https://irregularmigration.eu/poland/>
- Portugal: <https://irregularmigration.eu/portugal/>
- Serbia: <https://irregularmigration.eu/serbia/>
- Spain: <https://irregularmigration.eu/spain/>
- Tunisia: <https://irregularmigration.eu/tunisia/>
- Türkiye: <https://irregularmigration.eu/turkiye/>
- United Kingdom: <https://irregularmigration.eu/united-kingdom/>
- United States: <https://irregularmigration.eu/united-states/>

The subsequent sections of this report present brief descriptions and still images (screenshots) of the Data Portal and country pages.¹

¹ Accurate at time of publication.

2. THE INFOGRAPHICS WE PRODUCED

2.1 THE DATA PORTAL

As described above, the Data Portal provides a visual overview of the key estimates of the irregular migrant population in all countries where estimates were found. It shows the most recent, highest quality estimate from between 2008 and 2023 as compiled and assessed by the MIRreM project, and, where possible, a benchmark estimate from the Clandestino project in 2008 (Kierans and Vargas-Silva, 2024; Vogel and Kovacheva, 2008). For the more recent estimate, it presents the high and low figures of the range, if available. Otherwise, the central or singular figure is visualised in the high and low bands. All of the estimates from Clandestino come with a high and a low estimate.

Users can hover their cursor over any of the shaded countries on the map to bring up the estimated number of irregular migrants for that country. Clicking on a shaded country produces a small box with the country name, the year and quality of the most recent estimate, and a link to the relevant country page (see 2.2 below).

It is also possible to toggle between 1. the estimated number of irregular migrants, 2. the estimated number of irregular migrants *as a share of the total population of the country* and 3. the estimated number of irregular migrants *as a share of the foreign-born population of the country*, that was born in countries outside of free movement protocols (at the time of the estimate).

The Data Portal also provides top line findings from the WP4 working paper, a note on the methodology and limitations of the data, links to relevant publications from across the project, and a list of links to the individual country pages.

The dashboard is designed to be accessible a) for people who are colour blind (Kilin, 2022; Simplified Science Publishing, n.d.) and b) on a variety of device types (e.g. desktop, tablet, mobile).

2.2 THE COUNTRY PAGES

While the Data Portal presents an overview of key estimates and findings about the countries studied by MIRreM, as well as publications related to the project's data collection and assessment efforts (Vargas-Silva et al., 2025), it does not provide the full range of irregular migration estimates that were compiled and analysed under the MIRreM project. This more detailed information – when available² – is provided on the country pages, which:

- Visualise all of the stocks estimates compiled and assessed in the public database for that specific country, by number, share of the total population and share of the foreign-born population.³ These interactive charts include sources and notes.
- Host a data table that lays out the variables visualised in the charts. It is viewable within a browser window and also can be downloaded in .xlsx format.
- Provide a brief description of the methodology used, a note about the limitations of the data, links to resources that dive more deeply into these issues, including the aforementioned working paper and the full database on irregular migration stock estimates.
- Highlight publications from across the project that refer to the country in question.

Although the Data Portal and country pages are intended to be viewed and experienced online, still images (screenshots) of the content are displayed in Annex I for the sake of documentation.

² There were no estimates of the irregular migration stock between 2008 and 2023 found for Bosnia and Herzegovina, Morocco, Serbia, Tunisia or Türkiye. Therefore, there are no charts on the respective country pages.

³ The foreign-born population not covered by free movement protocols.

3. CONCLUSION

The visualisation tools developed under WP4 are designed to support MIRreM's broader mission of promoting the responsible use and interpretation of data on irregular migration. The Data Portal and country pages present estimates in a format that is accessible, transparent, and user-friendly, offering multiple entry points into the project's findings and encouraging engagement from a wide range of stakeholders.

Importantly, they also expose the complexity and limitations of the available data by framing visualisations through the outcomes of MIRreM's quality assessment. That is, not all estimates are equally robust or reliable. By making these distinctions visible, the tools invite users to approach irregular migration data critically, rather than accepting figures at face value.

ANNEX I

Figure 1: The Data Portal

WHO

The Mirrem project examined irregular migration estimates in 20 countries in Europe, North America and North Africa between 2008 and 2023. It follows in the steps of the Clandestino project, which carried out a similar exercise in 12 European countries between 2000 and 2008.

Interested users are encouraged to:

- Explore the interactive map for the most recent, highest quality estimates.
- Read up the findings and find related publications below the map.
- Visit individual country pages to view additional estimates (click on a country in the map for the relevant link or see the list of countries below the map).
- Press the 'Add Content' icon below.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

For information about the limitations of the data, the quality assessment criteria and cross-country findings, see the report, *The Irregular Migrant Populations of European States and Territories*, 2024.

INTERACTIVE MAP

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (not covered by the assessment protocol). In all cases, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the European Union level.

See full data

The Mirrem Public Data Portal on Irregular Migration Stocks

How to use this data portal and other reports below to explore the data

COUNTRY PAGES

MIRREM identified, compiled and assessed estimates of the irregular migration stock in the 20 countries listed in blue below. Click on the country name to explore these data and other country-relevant MIRREM reports. For the 10 countries listed in grey, no estimates were found. On these pages, only the country-relevant reports produced by the project are presented.

ALGERIA	GERMANY	GREECE
ARABIA SAUDI AND HERZEGOVINA	IRELAND	ITALY
BELGIUM	NETHERLANDS	NETHERLANDS
CANADA	POLAND	NETHERLANDS
FRANCE	PORTUGAL	NETHERLANDS
GERMANY		NETHERLANDS

TOP LINE FINDINGS

- Based on the most recent estimates in the Database, there were between 2.8 million and 3.2 million estimated irregular migrants living in 20 European countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and the UK) over the period 2018 and 2023.
- This figure represents less than 1% of the total population and between 1% and 20% of the foreign-born population from countries outside of the European Area for EU countries and the Common Travel Area for Ireland and the UK.
- Amongst the countries studied by the Mirrem project, the United States has the largest estimated irregular migration population (not only in terms of absolute numbers, but relative to its total and foreign-born populations).
- Ireland has the second smallest irregular migration population in terms of its size and its share of the total and foreign-born populations amongst the countries set covered.
- Of the 20 countries covered, an estimate of all were found for 5 countries (all 'border countries' as conceptualised within the project) and only 2 estimates of poor quality were found for Canada.
- Taking the estimates produced under the Clandestino project as a baseline, there was an additive change in the estimated number of irregular migrants across the 20 European countries since 2008.
- At the individual country level, however, many of the estimated irregular migration populations across borders appear to have changed:
 - Decreases in Austria, Germany and Spain
 - No change in Belgium, France, Italy, the UK and the US
 - Decreases in Finland, Greece, Ireland, Netherlands and Portugal.
- The countries with the largest estimated irregular migrant populations in Europe (the UK and Germany) have some of the most outdated estimates and represent a significant gap in the knowledge base.
- There is a need for consistent and more frequent estimates of the irregular migrant population in Europe, an area that could be addressed by Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union.

Related publications:

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Figure 2: Austria, country page

AUSTRIA

Figures on this page present estimates of Austria's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Recent surveys related to Austria are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population and contrasted to low, medium and high quality. Those who score high in countries include EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who score low in countries of the Common Travel Area, etc.

[Policy brief](#) [Publications](#)

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: These estimates are based on the number of irregular migration estimates, which are compiled and assessed as low, medium, or high quality. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population.

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: These scatter plots show the percentage of irregular migrants, which is compiled and assessed as low, medium, or high quality. The percentage of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population. The percentage of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population. The percentage of irregular migrants is estimated as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population.

DATA TABLE

30 entries per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Share of Total Population	Share of Foreign-Born Population
2008	10,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2009	12,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2010	15,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2011	18,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2012	20,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2013	22,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2014	25,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2015	28,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2016	30,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2017	32,000	Low	0.1%	0.2%
2018	45,000	High	0.1%	0.3%
2019	50,000	High	0.1%	0.3%
2020	55,000	High	0.1%	0.3%
2021	60,000	High	0.1%	0.3%
2022	70,000	High	0.1%	0.3%
2023	65,000	High	0.1%	0.3%

[Download this table.xls](#)

METHODS

Figures on this page present estimates of Austria's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and books, related to Austria are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (or contrasted to low, medium and high quality). Those who score high in countries include EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who score low in countries of the Common Travel Area, etc.

The Estimate Quality brings together aspects of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and consistency data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 6 and 8 points were graded as low quality
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were assessed as medium quality
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and algorithmic limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a single, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migration Population of Europe, Africa and the Middle East, 2024.

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality metrics that comprise the aggregate quality score for Austria and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Austria:

[See all publications](#)

Figure 3: Belgium, country page

BELGIUM

Figures on this page present estimates of Belgium's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Belgium are presented below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the assessment process. (As in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EU, the Americas and the Caribbean and the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area) - [see here](#)

Policy brief
Publications

Source: See notes for details on the quality of the estimates, which are completed and assessed by the MIRREM project. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process.

Source: See notes for details on the quality of the estimates, which are completed and assessed by the MIRREM project. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process. The quality of the estimates is assessed based on the MIRREM project's assessment process.

DATA TABLE

201 - entered per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Assessment	Notes
2008	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2009	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2010	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2011	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2012	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2013	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2014	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2015	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2016	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2017	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2018	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2019	50,000	Low	Low	Initial estimate with low quality assessment.
2020	100,000	High	High	High estimate with high quality assessment.
2021	100,000	High	High	High estimate with high quality assessment.
2022	100,000	High	High	High estimate with high quality assessment.
2023	100,000	High	High	High estimate with high quality assessment.

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Belgium's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Belgium are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the assessment process. (As in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EU, the Americas and the Caribbean and the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area).

The Estimate Quality brings together aspects of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 12 points were assessed as medium quality.
- Estimates that received evaluations of 12 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a single, the single or central figure is provided as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the [MIRREM Working Paper: The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe \(2024\)](#) and [MIRREM Working Paper: The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe \(2024\)](#).

Access the [full dataset](#), which includes the assessments of the full quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Belgium and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Belgium:

Substantive opportunities for irregular migrants and refugees

Public Database on Irregular Migration (DAMI) version 2.0

The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe

How to use the available data on irregular migration for policymaking

Public Database on Irregular Migration (DAMI) version 1.0

BELGIUM - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

Using Mobility Data To Understand The Scale Of The Irregular Migrant Population

Pathways And Public Evaluation: Comparative National-Level And Public-Accession-Level Metrics

[See all publications](#)

Figure 4: Bosnia and Herzegovina, country page

Figure 5: Canada, country page

Figure 6: Finland, country page

FINLAND

Figures on this page present estimates of Finland's irregular migration population between 2010 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Finland are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area. See 2023

[Policy brief](#)
[Publications](#)

Note: The number of irregular residents is based on the number of irregular migration estimates, which are presented as estimates of the number of irregular residents in the country. The number of irregular residents is based on the number of irregular migration estimates, which are presented as estimates of the number of irregular residents in the country. The number of irregular residents is based on the number of irregular migration estimates, which are presented as estimates of the number of irregular residents in the country.

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DATA TABLE

20 | entries per page

Year	Low Estimate	High Estimate	Quality	Assessment	Notes
2010	1000	1000	1	Low	
2011	1000	1000	1	Low	
2012	1000	1000	1	Low	
2013	1000	1000	1	Low	
2014	1000	1000	1	Low	
2015	1000	1000	1	Low	
2016	1000	1000	1	Low	
2017	1000	1000	1	Low	
2018	10000	10000	2	Medium	
2019	15000	15000	2	Medium	
2020	20000	20000	2	Medium	
2021	30000	30000	2	Medium	
2022	90000	95000	3	High	
2023	70000	75000	3	High	

1 2 3

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Finland's irregular migration population between 2010 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Finland are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area.

The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, workability, reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and no high or 10 points were appraised as medium quality.
- Estimates that exceeded evaluations of 10 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality.

Users should note: Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimates.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migration Population of Europe, Africa and the Middle East, 2024.

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Finland and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Finland:

MIRREM 2024

Public database on irregular migration (Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland) 2010-2023

MIRREM 2024

The Irregular Migration Population of Europe

MIRREM 2024

How IR is the available data on irregular migration for the information?

MIRREM 2024

Public database on irregular migration (Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland) 2010-2023

MIRREM 2024

Public database on irregular migration (Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland) 2010-2023

MIRREM 2024

Public database on irregular migration (Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland) 2010-2023

MIRREM 2024

Public database on irregular migration (Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland) 2010-2023

[See all publications](#)

Figure 7: France, country page

FRANCE

Figures on this page present estimates of France's irregular migrant population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and derived from under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to France are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (not covered by free movement policies, i.e., all Europe those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). 2025-2025

Policy brief
Publications

DATA TABLE

10 entries per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Assessment	Notes
2008	150,000	4	Low	
2009	180,000	4	Low	
2010	200,000	4	Low	
2011	220,000	4	Low	
2012	250,000	4	Low	
2013	280,000	4	Low	
2014	300,000	4	Low	
2015	320,000	4	Low	
2016	350,000	4	Low	
2017	380,000	4	Low	
2018	400,000	4	Low	
2019	420,000	4	Low	
2020	450,000	4	Low	
2021	480,000	4	Low	
2022	500,000	4	Low	
2023	520,000	4	Low	

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METHODS

Figures on this page present estimates of France's irregular migrant population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and derived from under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to France are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (not covered by free movement policies, i.e., all Europe those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area).

The Estimate Quality brings together assessments of an estimator's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were assigned as medium quality.
- Estimates that exceeded evaluations of 10 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the [MIRREM Working Paper: The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe \(France and Europe\) 2025](#).

Access the [full dataset](#), which includes the assessments of the full quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for France and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to France:

Migration on behalf of others: what extent and how are their working and living conditions?

Working conditions for irregular migrants and refugees

Public Database on Irregular Migration in Europe and Africa

The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe

How is the available data on irregular migration in the Netherlands?

Public database on irregular migration: estimates from the Netherlands

FRANCE - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

Pathways and Policy Evaluation: Comparative National Laws and Policies Addressing Irregular Migration

[See all publications](#)

Figure 8: Germany, country page

GERMANY

Figures on this page present estimates of Germany's irregular migration population between 2018 and 2022 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Germany are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (if covered by that measurement period). E.g. 28.8 million, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the continent's 'border area'.

Policy brief
Publications

Note: The number of irregular migrants in Germany is estimated using a combination of administrative data, high-quality surveys, and other sources. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants.

Note: The number of irregular migrants in Germany is estimated using a combination of administrative data, high-quality surveys, and other sources. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants. The number of irregular migrants is estimated as the difference between the total population and the population of regular migrants.

DATA TABLE

30 entries per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Assessment	Notes
2018	288,000	High	High	
2019	312,000	High	High	
2020	336,000	High	High	
2021	360,000	High	High	
2022	384,000	High	High	

1 2

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Germany's irregular migration population between 2018 and 2022 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Germany are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (if covered by that measurement period). E.g. 28.8 million, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the continent's 'border area'.

The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score (see text).

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were appraised as medium quality.
- Estimates that received valuations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality.

There should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migration Population of Europe (MIRREM Working Paper 2024).

Across the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Germany and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Germany:

Public Database on Irregular Migration: The Estimates and Indicators (MIRREM 2024)

Discussion, narratives and country case studies on irregular migration

The Irregular Migration Population of Europe

How to use the available data on irregular migration

Public Database on Irregular Migration: Country Briefs on Irregular Migration

Germany - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

Pathways and Policy Evaluation: Country Case Studies and Public Addressing Irregular Migration

Do countries the Study of Irregular Migration and Irregular Migration Policies in Europe and Beyond (MIRREM 2024)

[See all publications](#)

Figure 9: Greece, country page

GREECE

Figures on this page present estimates of Greece's irregular migration population between 2007 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Greece are grouped here.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the investment process (i.e. in Europe, those who were born in countries outside EU/EFTA/EEA/US and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). - 06/2025

Policy brief
Publications

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: The tables in this page show the number of irregular migration estimates, which are compiled and presented here under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Greece are displayed on this page. The data displayed on this page are based on the best available information. The data are subject to change as more information becomes available. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data.

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: The tables in this page show the number of irregular migration estimates, which are compiled and presented here under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Greece are displayed on this page. The data displayed on this page are based on the best available information. The data are subject to change as more information becomes available. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data. The data are presented as a range of estimates to reflect the uncertainty in the data.

DATA TABLE

20 | entries per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Assessment	Comments
2007	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2008	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2009	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2010	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2011	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2012	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2013	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2014	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2015	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2016	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2017	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2018	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2019	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2020	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2021	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2022	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate
2023	150,000	4	Low	Low quality estimate

1

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Greece's irregular migration population between 2007 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Greece are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the investment process (i.e. in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimator's accessibility, documentation, methodology, visibility and underlying data into an aggregate score and rank:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were appraised as medium quality
- Estimates that exceeded evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is reported as both the high and low estimates.

For more information on this data set, please contact the MIRREM team. Please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe (London and Paris: IOM, 2024).

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Greece and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Greece:

Public Disasters as Irregular Migration (The Estimates and Evidence)

The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe

How IR is to be available and an immediate estimate for information

Public Disasters as Irregular Migration (The Estimates and Evidence)

GREECE - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

Returns and Policy Evaluation: Connecting National Laws and Policies Addressing Irregular Migrants

Do existing the Study of Irregular Returns and the Migration Policies in Europe and Beyond (2022-2023)

[See all publications](#)

Figure 10: Ireland, country page

IRELAND

Figures on this page present estimates of Ireland's irregular migration population between 2010 and 2022 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Ireland are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a bar chart, as a share of the total population and as a share of EU foreign-born population and carried out by the Government of Ireland (G.I.). Citizens, those who were born in countries outside of EU, Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area - 200-2020

[Policy brief](#)
[Publications](#)

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

As a share of the total population

As a share of the foreign-born population*

DATA TABLE

Year	Low estimate	High estimate	Quality score	Assessment	Comments
2010	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2011	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2012	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2013	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2014	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2015	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2016	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2017	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2018	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2019	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2020	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2021	20000	30000	4	Low quality	
2022	20000	30000	4	Low quality	

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Ireland's irregular migration population between 2010 and 2022 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Ireland are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a bar chart, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population. Carried out by the Government of Ireland (G.I.). Citizens, those who were born in countries outside of EU, Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area.

The Estimates Quality brings together aspects of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data in an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were appraised as medium quality.
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimates.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper: The Irregular Migration Population of Europe (Marrero and Trogo-Dias, 2024).

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Ireland and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Ireland:

Public Estimates on Irregular Migration (Low, Medium and High Quality)

2024-07-24

The Irregular Migration Population of Europe

2024-07-24

How fit is the available data on irregular migration for assessment?

2024-07-24

Public database on irregular migration: which estimates data will be used?

2024-07-24

IRLAND - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

2024-07-24

Pathways and Public Evaluation Committee (PEV) and Public Advisory Committee (PAC)

2024-07-24

[See all publications](#)

Figure 11: Italy, country page

ITALY

Figures on this page present estimates of Italy's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM activities related to Italy are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the common Travel Area). 2008-2023

Policy brief
Publications

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

As a share of the total population

As a share of the foreign-born population*

DATA TABLE

30 entries per page

Year	Low estimate	High estimate	As a share of the total population	As a share of the foreign-born population*
2008	500,000	500,000	0.8%	1.2%
2009	550,000	550,000	0.9%	1.3%
2010	600,000	600,000	1.0%	1.4%
2011	650,000	650,000	1.1%	1.5%
2012	700,000	700,000	1.2%	1.6%
2013	750,000	750,000	1.3%	1.7%
2014	800,000	800,000	1.4%	1.8%
2015	850,000	850,000	1.5%	1.9%
2016	900,000	900,000	1.6%	2.0%
2017	950,000	950,000	1.7%	2.1%
2018	1,000,000	1,000,000	1.8%	2.2%
2019	1,050,000	1,050,000	1.9%	2.3%
2020	1,100,000	1,100,000	2.0%	2.4%
2021	1,150,000	1,150,000	2.1%	2.5%
2022	1,200,000	1,200,000	2.2%	2.6%
2023	1,250,000	1,250,000	2.3%	2.7%

METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Italy's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Italy are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the common Travel Area). 2008-2023

The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimator's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data via an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were appraised as medium quality
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality

WORKING PAPERS

Working papers are preliminary documents that are not intended for publication. They are subject to change and should not be cited. They are available for download on the MIRREM website.

Publications related to Italy:

High-level overview of irregular migration in Italy

Working Paper

Public Database on Irregular Migration in Europe

Public Database

Estimate Quality

Working Paper

Public Database on Irregular Migration in Europe

Public Database

Estimate Quality

Working Paper

Public Database on Irregular Migration in Europe

Public Database

Estimate Quality

Working Paper

Public Database on Irregular Migration in Europe

Public Database

[See all publications](#)

Figure 12: Morocco, country page

MOROCCO
The MIRREM project was unable to locate estimates of Morocco's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2022. Project outputs related to Morocco are compiled below.

[Policy brief](#) [Publications](#)

Publications related to Morocco:

- DIGN FIRM**
Dignity For Irregular Migrants in EU Frontline Labour Markets
October 2021 - 7 April 2022 (54 weeks)
- MIRREM - Country Brief on Morocco**
- Migration and Policy Evaluation: Comparative National Laws And Policies Addressing Irregular Migration**
- Re-centring the Study of Migration: Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond (MIRREM)**

[See all publications](#)

Figure 13: The Netherlands, country page

THE NETHERLANDS

Figures on this page present estimates of the Netherlands' irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Netherlands are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (see Country Data Measurement page 6). If unclear, those only who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area... see page 6.

[Policy brief](#)
[Publications](#)

DATA TABLE

23 entries per page

Year	Low Estimate	High Estimate	Quality Score	Assessment
2008	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2009	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2010	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2011	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2012	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2013	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2014	10000	10000	8	Medium quality
2015	10000	25000	8	Medium quality
2016	10000	25000	8	Medium quality
2017	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2018	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2019	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2020	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2021	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2022	10000	20000	8	Medium quality
2023	10000	20000	8	Medium quality

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of the Netherlands' irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Clear MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Netherlands are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population (see Country Data Measurement page 6). If unclear, those only who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area.

The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data (see an aggregate score and legend).

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were assessed as medium quality.
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were considered as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these estimates compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe: Methods and Insights (July, 2024).

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Netherlands and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Netherlands:

Migration on behalf of migrants: which extent and how do we measure it?

Disruptive migration as a by-product of international trade and investment: the case of the Netherlands

Public Statistics on Irregular Migration: The Netherlands and Indicators That are of Interest to the Netherlands

Dimension, uncertainty and quality: assessing an irregular migration estimate

The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe

How is the available data on irregular migration for policymaking?

Public statistics on irregular migration: the Netherlands and other countries

NETHERLANDS - Country Brief on Irregular Migration

[See all publications](#)

Figure 14: Poland, country page

POLAND

Figures on this page present estimates of Poland's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM experts related to Poland are listed below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population that arrived in their destination country (i.e., all those those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). [View 2023](#)

Policy brief
Publications

Notes: This table lists the quality of the estimates, which are categorized and summarized by the quality of the estimates. The quality of the estimates is based on the quality of the data used to estimate the irregular migration population. The quality of the estimates is based on the quality of the data used to estimate the irregular migration population. The quality of the estimates is based on the quality of the data used to estimate the irregular migration population.

DATA TABLE

30 entries per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Share of Total Population	Share of Foreign-Born Population
2008	10,000	Low	0.0001	0.05
2009	12,000	Low	0.0001	0.06
2010	15,000	Low	0.0001	0.07
2011	18,000	Low	0.0001	0.08
2012	20,000	Low	0.0001	0.09
2013	22,000	Low	0.0001	0.10
2014	25,000	Low	0.0001	0.11
2015	28,000	Low	0.0001	0.12
2016	30,000	Low	0.0001	0.13
2017	32,000	Low	0.0001	0.14
2018	35,000	Low	0.0001	0.15
2019	38,000	Low	0.0001	0.16
2020	40,000	Low	0.0001	0.17
2021	45,000	Low	0.0001	0.18
2022	50,000	Low	0.0001	0.19
2023	70,000	High	0.0001	0.20

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Poland's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were completed and carried out under the MIRREM project. Clear MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Poland are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by the movement policies (i.e., all those those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). The Estimate Quality brings together appraisals of an estimate's reliability, representativeness, methodological rigour and employment data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were assigned to medium quality.
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality.

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is reported as both the high and low estimate. For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper: The Irregular Migration Population of Europe (Giles and Hogg, 2020).

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Poland and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Poland:

Public Evidence on Irregular Migration: Data, Estimates and Indicators Data April 2024.pdf

The Irregular Migration Population of Europe

How EU is the available data on irregular migration for policy-makers?

Public Evidence on Irregular Migration: Data, Estimates and Indicators Data April 2024.pdf

AF **FPI**

Int Returns in Policies

See all publications

Figure 15: Portugal, country page

PORTUGAL

Figures on this page present estimates of Portugal's irregular migration population between 2009 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Portugal are grouped below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by free movement policies (i.e., in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland; those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area)... see page

[Policy brief](#) [Publications](#)

Notes: This table refers to the number of irregular migration estimates, which are considered as countries (Belgium, D., Spain, France, G., Germany, H., Greece, I., Italy, L., Lithuania, N., Netherlands, P., Poland, S., Sweden, T., United Kingdom, U., USA, V., Vietnam, Y.). The high and low estimates are based on the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Portugal are displayed on this page.

Notes: This table refers to the number of irregular migration estimates, which are considered as countries (Belgium, D., Spain, France, G., Germany, H., Greece, I., Italy, L., Lithuania, N., Netherlands, P., Poland, S., Sweden, T., United Kingdom, U., USA, V., Vietnam, Y.). The high and low estimates are based on the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Portugal are displayed on this page.

DATA TABLE

20 entries per page

Year	Country	Estimate	Low Estimate	High Estimate	Quality Score	Quality Assessment	Methodology	Comments
2009	Portugal	10000	5000	15000	4	Low quality
2010	Portugal	12000	6000	18000	4	Low quality
2011	Portugal	15000	7500	22500	4	Low quality
2012	Portugal	18000	9000	27000	4	Low quality
2013	Portugal	22000	11000	33000	4	Low quality
2014	Portugal	28000	14000	42000	4	Low quality
2015	Portugal	35000	17500	52500	4	Low quality
2016	Portugal	45000	22500	67500	4	Low quality
2017	Portugal	60000	30000	90000	4	Low quality
2018	Portugal	80000	40000	120000	4	Low quality
2019	Portugal	100000	50000	150000	4	Low quality
2020	Portugal	120000	60000	180000	4	Low quality
2021	Portugal	150000	75000	225000	4	Low quality
2022	Portugal	200000	100000	300000	4	Low quality
2023	Portugal	250000	125000	375000	4	Low quality

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METHODOLOGY

Figures on this page present estimates of Portugal's irregular migration population between 2009 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Portugal are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by free movement policies (i.e., in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland; those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area).

The Estimate Quality brings together assessments of an estimate's accessibility, documentation, methodology, reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were appraised as medium quality
- Estimates that exceeded evaluations of 10 points (up to the maximum score of 12 points) were classified as high quality

Users should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were developed and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migration Population of Europe (Morris and Higgins-Gins, 2020).

Access the MIR dataset, which includes the assessments of the final quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Portugal and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Portugal:

The number of irregular immigrants in Europe has remained the same for 26 years and increases less than 1% of the population

[See all publications](#)

Figure 16: Serbia, country page

Figure 17: Spain, country page

SPAIN

Figures on this page present estimates of Spain's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to Spain are provided below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population that arrived in the destination population (i.e., all foreign-born who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). [View 2023](#)

[Policy brief](#) [Publications](#)

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: This table is based on the number of irregular migrant population, which is composed of countries such as, Italy, France, Germany, the UK, Spain, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, and others. The number of irregular migrants is estimated based on the number of irregular migrants who arrived in the destination population (i.e., all foreign-born who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). [View 2023](#)

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: This table is based on the number of irregular migrants, which is composed of countries such as, Italy, France, Germany, the UK, Spain, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, and others. The number of irregular migrants is estimated based on the number of irregular migrants who arrived in the destination population (i.e., all foreign-born who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area). [View 2023](#)

DATA TABLE

30 entries per page

Year	Country	Estimate	Quality	As a share of total population	As a share of foreign-born population
2008	Spain	75000	4	0.15	0.35
2009	Spain	45000	4	0.10	0.25
2010	Spain	40000	4	0.08	0.22
2011	Spain	35000	4	0.07	0.20
2012	Spain	25000	4	0.05	0.15
2013	Spain	15000	4	0.03	0.10
2014	Spain	10000	4	0.02	0.07
2015	Spain	10000	4	0.02	0.07
2016	Spain	10000	4	0.02	0.07
2017	Spain	10000	4	0.02	0.07
2018	Spain	45000	5	0.09	0.18
2019	Spain	55000	5	0.11	0.22
2020	Spain	50000	5	0.10	0.20
2021	Spain	35000	5	0.07	0.15
2022	Spain	25000	5	0.05	0.10
2023	Spain	35000	5	0.07	0.15

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METHODS

Figures on this page present estimates of Spain's irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to Spain are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population or equivalently the resident population (i.e., all foreign-born who were born in countries outside of EU Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area).

The Estimate Quality brings together assessments of an estimate's availability, documentation, methodology, reliability and whether data into an aggregate score and band:

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 10 points were assessed as medium quality
- Estimates that received evaluations of 10 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality

Users should note: Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, an estimate does not include a single, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimates.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe, Germany and France, 2024.

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the five quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for Spain and all other countries covered by the MIRREM project.

Publications related to Spain:

[See all publications](#)

Figure 18: Tunisia, country page

Figure 19: Türkiye, country page

Figure 21: The United States, country page

UNITED STATES

Figures on this page present estimates of the United States' irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. MIRREM outputs related to the US are presented below.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by free movement policies (i.e., in Europe, those who have been in countries outside of EFTA Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area) – see page 10.

[Policy brief](#) [Publications](#)

ESTIMATED NUMBER OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: See heading for details on the sources of the irregular migration estimates, which are presented as central estimates (C), lower estimates (L) and higher estimates (H). Quality scores are presented as low (L), medium (M) and high (H). The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration. The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration. The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration.

ESTIMATED PERCENTAGE OF IRREGULAR MIGRANTS BY YEAR

Notes: See heading for details on the sources of the irregular migration estimates, which are presented as central estimates (C), lower estimates (L) and higher estimates (H). Quality scores are presented as low (L), medium (M) and high (H). The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration. The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration. The quality scores are based on the MIRREM project's assessment of the quality of the data used to estimate irregular migration.

DATA TABLE

201 estimates per page

Year	Estimate	Quality	Source	Notes
2008	12	High
2009	11	High
2010	10	High
2011	11	High
2012	12	High
2013	11	High
2014	10	High
2015	11	High
2016	12	High
2017	11	High
2018	10	High
2019	11	High
2020	10	High
2021	11	High
2022	10	High
2023	11	High

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METHODS

Figures on this page present estimates of the United States' irregular migration population between 2008 and 2023 and corresponding assessments of their quality, which were compiled and carried out under the MIRREM project. Other MIRREM outputs, such as working papers and briefs, related to US are displayed on this page.

Estimates can be viewed as a number, as a share of the total population and as a share of the foreign-born population not covered by free movement policies (i.e., in Europe, those who were born in countries outside of EFTA Free Movement and in the UK and Ireland, those who were born outside of the Common Travel Area).

The Estimate Quality brings together assessments of an estimate's accessibility, representativeness, methodological reliability and underlying data into an aggregate score and band.

- Estimates that scored between 4 and 8 points were graded as low quality.
- Estimates that received scores greater than 8 points and as high as 12 points were assigned as medium quality.
- Estimates that exceeded calculations of 12 points up to the maximum score of 12 points were classified as high quality.

Other should note:

Irregular migration estimates come with inherent uncertainty and significant limitations. Comparisons between estimates should be interpreted with particular caution.

On this page, if an estimate does not include a range, the single or central figure is recorded as both the high and low estimate.

For more information on how these data were compiled and assessed, please refer to the MIRREM Working Paper, The Single-Issue Migration Population of European States and Irregular Status (2024).

Access the full dataset, which includes the assessments of the true quality criteria that comprise the aggregate quality score for USA and all other countries covered by the approach.

Publications related to United States:

- Migration: the impact of and what extent and how they're working and not working
- Research: Evidence on behalf of irregular workers. To what extent and how are they working?
- Public database on irregular migration: Flow Estimates and Indicators (State and territory)
- Public database on irregular migration: stock estimates (Data and metadata)
- USA: Country Brief on Irregular Migration
- Publications And Policy Briefing: Countries National Laws And Public Administration Practices
- How far is the available data on irregular migration?
- Alternative approaches to measuring irregular migration
- Research approaches: Divergent Approaches to Measuring Irregular Migration

[See all publications](#)

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